

Revisit Calculation and Waveform Control for a Multifunction Radar

G.A. Watson and W.D. Blair

Code B32

Naval Surface Warfare Center Dahlgren Division
Dahlgren, Virginia 22448-5000

Abstract

Since phased array radars have the ability to perform adaptive sampling of the target trajectory by the radar beam positioning, proper control of the radar has the potential for significantly improving many aspects associated with the tracking of multiple maneuvering targets. The technique proposed in this paper uses the Interacting Multiple Model (IMM) algorithm to track maneuvering targets and control the revisit time, and pointing, and adjust the energy level of the radar. Since the output of the IMM algorithm better represents the accuracy of the state estimates during a maneuver than that of a single model filter, the IMM algorithm is used to compute an on-line measure of tracking performance to determine the revisit time of the next track update in order to maintain a given level of performance. The revisit time is computed as the one positive root of a polynomial equation of the sample period. The model probabilities of the IMM algorithm are also used to schedule the energy level of a radar dwell. As a result, the revisit times are a function of track filter performance and the target trajectory. Algorithms for computing the revisit time, pointing the radar, and adjusting the energy level using the output of the IMM algorithm are presented in this paper. Performance comparisons are given for the IMM algorithm using a constant data rate, adjusted energy levels, and an adaptive data rate.

1. Introduction

Since a phased array radar can direct the radar beam in any direction without physically moving the radar antenna, it can perform adaptive sampling of the target trajectory. Proper control of the beam pointing can significantly improve the tracking of multiple maneuvering targets. Current methods for radar control use decision-directed techniques to perform adaptive sampling. However, in most systems only a few data rates are available and the selection of the data rate often does not reflect target maneuvers, missed detections, and the strength of the return. The track is updated at an assigned data rate, whether or not that rate is required to maintain a given or desired level of performance. By changing the revisit time continually, a measurement is scheduled only when needed. However, single model track filters possess the drawback when used to determine the update rate for maneuvering targets [1].

Since the tracking of maneuvering targets with single model track filters is rather poor, decision-directed techniques have been employed to improve the accuracy of the state estimates during target maneuvers. One decision-directed technique for tracking maneuvering targets increases the variance of the acceleration error during a maneuver to reduce the bias in the state estimates [2]. This technique has two major problems. First, the filter response is significantly delayed because the variance of the acceleration error is not increased until the maneuver is detected. Second, after a target stops maneuvering, the decision to reduce the acceleration error is often delayed because the filter with a large acceleration error variance may not have a detectable bias during or after the maneuver. When tracking with a single model filter, an assessment of filter performance determines the update rate for decision-directed approaches to adaptive sampling. A common technique for assessing filter performance involves analyzing the filter residuals and declaring a maneuver when the residuals are larger than a threshold. When the residuals are below the threshold, the track is updated at a lower frequency.

A revisit calculation based on the predicted measurement, the

predicted error covariance, and relative track accuracy is presented in [3], where the next revisit time is determined to be the time when the major axis of the ellipsoid defined by the predicted error covariance is above a threshold. This technique avoids decision-directed logic concerning the sample rate but has an error covariance that does not reflect the accuracy of the state estimates during target maneuvers. A revisit technique that responds to target maneuvers and avoids the decision-directed approach for both tracking maneuvering targets and sample rate adjustment can be accomplished using the Interacting Multiple Model (IMM) algorithm.

The IMM algorithm is an effective technique for tracking targets flying at high speeds and performing maneuvers [4,5]. The results of previous investigations indicate that the IMM algorithm is the superior technique for tracking maneuvering targets when the computational requirements of other techniques are considered [5,6,7]. The IMM algorithm uses multiple models that interact through state mixing to track a target through an arbitrary maneuver. Governed by an underlying Markov chain, the state estimates are mixed according to their model probabilities and model switching probabilities. The output estimate is a probabilistic sum of the individual filter estimates and represents the relative performance of each model. The output error covariance also reflects the tracking performance during a maneuver because it is calculated to match the mixed Gaussian density based on the output of the individual filters. The output of the IMM algorithm can be used to determine the revisit time for the next measurement that is computed as the time the predicted error covariance exceeds a given threshold of performance. The revisit time is the one positive root of a polynomial equation in the revisit period. When the target is maneuvering, the revisit time between measurements will be smaller than when the target is not maneuvering. The on-line measure of performance will automatically take into account the previously mentioned factors such as target range and missed detections. The scheduling of energy waveforms can also be accomplished using the output of the IMM algorithm. When the target maneuvers, the constant velocity model probability is low and changing to a higher energy waveform should provide better state estimates because the measurement error is reduced. After the maneuver, tracking with a lower energy waveform can be resumed to conserve the radar time-energy budget. When using the IMM algorithm, the revisit time is a function of the tracking performance and is more flexible than decision-directed approaches.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents some background material, while Section 3 describes the IMM algorithm. Section 4 outlines the dynamic motion models and the kinematic constraint for constant speed targets. The algorithms for calculating the revisit time, pointing the radar, and adjusting the energy levels using the IMM algorithm are presented in Sections 5, 6, and 7, respectively. Section 8 presents simulation results, and concluding remarks are given in Section 9.

2. Background

The discrete-time model for a dynamic system is given by

$$X_k = F_{k-1}X_{k-1} + G_{k-1}w_{k-1} \quad (2.1)$$

$$Z_k = H_k X_k + v_k \quad (2.2)$$

where w_{k-1} is a process noise vector with $w_{k-1} \sim N(0, Q_{k-1})$, v_k is a measurement error vector with $v_k \sim N(0, R_k)$, X_k is a state vector, and Z_k is a measurement vector. The Kalman filter algorithm is commonly used to estimate the state and error

covariance of the system from the measurements. The equations for the Kalman filter are outlined as follows.

Time Update:

$$X_{k|k-1} = F_{k-1}X_{k-1|k-1} \quad (2.3)$$

$$P_{k|k-1} = F_{k-1}P_{k-1|k-1}F_{k-1}^T + G_{k-1}Q_{k-1}G_{k-1}^T \quad (2.4)$$

Measurement Update:

$$X_{k|k} = X_{k|k-1} + K_k\tilde{Z}_k \quad (2.5)$$

$$P_{k|k} = [I - K_kH_k]P_{k|k-1} \quad (2.6)$$

where

$$\tilde{Z}_k = Z_k - H_kX_{k|k-1} \quad (2.7)$$

$$K_k = P_{k|k-1}H_k^T S_k^{-1} \quad (2.8)$$

$$S_k = H_kP_{k|k-1}H_k^T + R_k \quad (2.9)$$

with X_{ij} and P_{ij} denoting the state estimate and error covariance for time i given measurements through time j .

3. The IMM Algorithm

An important problem is the state estimation of a linear system with Markovian switching coefficients. The system dynamics are represented by multiple models which are hypothesized to be correct. A linear system with Markovian switching coefficients can be represented as

$$X_k = F_{k-1}(\theta_k)X_{k-1} + G_{k-1}(\theta_k)w_{k-1} \quad (3.1)$$

$$Z_k = H_k(\theta_k)X_k + v_k \quad (3.2)$$

where θ_k is a finite state Markov chain taking values $\{1, \dots, N\}$ according to the probability p_{ij} of transitioning from model i to model j . The w_{k-1} and v_k are white Gaussian errors for the system state and measurement processes.

The IMM algorithm consists of a filter for each model, a model probability evaluator, an estimate mixer at the input of the filters, and an estimate combiner at the output of the filters. The multiple models interact through the mixing to track a target maneuvering through an arbitrary trajectory. A flow diagram of the IMM algorithm with two models is given in Fig. 3.1, where $X_{k|k}$ is the state estimate based on both models, $X_{k|k}^j$ is the state estimate based on model j , Λ_k is the vector of model likelihoods, and μ_k is a vector of model probabilities when all likelihoods are being considered. The mixer uses the model probabilities and model switching probabilities to compute a mixed estimate for each model. Each filter then uses a mixed estimate and measurement to compute a new estimate and likelihood for each model. The likelihoods, prior model probabilities, and model switching probabilities are used to compute new model probabilities. The overall state estimate is then computed with the new state estimates and their model probabilities. The IMM algorithm for tracking with N models is outlined in the following 5 steps. A derivation and detailed explanation of the IMM algorithm are given in [5,7].

Step 1: Mixing of State Estimates

The filtering process starts with state estimates $X_{k-1|k-1}^j$, error covariances $P_{k-1|k-1}^j$, and the associated probabilities μ_{k-1}^j for each model, M_k^j . The mixed state estimate and error covariance for M_k^j are computed as

$$X_{k-1|k-1}^{0j} = \sum_{i=1}^N X_{k-1|k-1}^i \mu_{k-1}^{ij} \quad (3.3)$$

$$P_{k-1|k-1}^{0j} = \sum_{i=1}^N \mu_{k-1}^{ij} [P_{k-1|k-1}^i + (X_{k-1|k-1}^i - X_{k-1|k-1}^{0j})(X_{k-1|k-1}^i - X_{k-1|k-1}^{0j})^T] \quad (3.4)$$

Fig. 3.1. The IMM Algorithm

where

$$\mu_{k-1|k-1}^{ij} = \frac{1}{c_j} p_{ij} \mu_{k-1}^i, \quad c_j = \sum_{i=1}^N p_{ij} \mu_{k-1}^i \quad (3.5)$$

Step 2: Model-Conditioned Updates

Kalman filtering equations provide model-conditioned updates.

Step 3: Model Likelihood Computations

The likelihood of M_k^j , Λ_k^j , is computed with \tilde{Z}_k^j , S_k^j , and the assumption of Gaussian statistics and is given by

$$\Lambda_k^j = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|2\pi S_k^j|}} \exp[-0.5(\tilde{Z}_k^j)^T (S_k^j)^{-1} \tilde{Z}_k^j] \quad (3.6)$$

Step 4: Model Probabilities Update

The model probabilities, μ_k^j , are updated as

$$\mu_k^j = \frac{1}{c} \Lambda_k^j \bar{c}_j, \quad c = \sum_{i=1}^N \Lambda_k^i \bar{c}_i \quad (3.7)$$

Step 5: Combination of State Estimates

The output state estimate and error covariance are given by

$$X_{k|k} = \sum_{i=1}^N X_{k|k}^i \mu_k^i \quad (3.8)$$

$$P_{k|k} = \sum_{i=1}^N \mu_k^i [P_{k|k}^i + (X_{k|k}^i - X_{k|k})(X_{k|k}^i - X_{k|k})^T] \quad (3.9)$$

4. Motion Models

A three model IMM algorithm for tracking maneuvering targets is used in this paper. The motion models are constant velocity (CV), exponentially increasing acceleration (EIA), and three dimensional turning rate (3DTR) and are combined to form the CVEIA3DTR track filter. In the development, CV is model 1, EIA is model 2, and 3DTR is model 3. The state estimates for the models at time k are

$$X_k^1 = [x_k^1 \quad \dot{x}_k^1 \quad y_k^1 \quad \dot{y}_k^1 \quad z_k^1 \quad \dot{z}_k^1]^T \quad (4.1)$$

$$X_k^i = [x_k^i \quad \dot{x}_k^i \quad \ddot{x}_k^i \quad y_k^i \quad \dot{y}_k^i \quad \ddot{y}_k^i \quad z_k^i \quad \dot{z}_k^i \quad \ddot{z}_k^i]^T, \quad i = 2, 3 \quad (4.2)$$

The discrete-time models are given by

$$F_k^i = \begin{bmatrix} B_k^i & 0_{j \times j} & 0_{j \times j} \\ 0_{j \times j} & B_k^i & 0_{j \times j} \\ 0_{j \times j} & 0_{j \times j} & B_k^i \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.3)$$

with

$$B_k^1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & T \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.4)$$

$$B_k^2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & T & \alpha^{-2}(e^{\alpha T} - 1 - \alpha T) \\ 0 & 1 & \alpha^{-1}(e^{\alpha T} - 1) \\ 0 & 0 & e^{\alpha T} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.5)$$

$$B_k^3 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \omega^{-1} \sin(\omega T) & \omega^{-2}(1 - \cos(\omega T)) \\ 0 & \cos(\omega T) & \omega^{-1} \sin(\omega T) \\ 0 & -\omega \sin(\omega T) & \cos(\omega T) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.6)$$

and

$$G_k^i = \begin{bmatrix} D_k^i & 0_{j \times 1} & 0_{j \times 1} \\ 0_{j \times 1} & D_k^i & 0_{j \times 1} \\ 0_{j \times 1} & 0_{j \times 1} & D_k^i \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.7)$$

with

$$D_k^1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 T^2 \\ T \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.8)$$

$$D_k^2 = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha^{-3}(e^{\alpha T} - 1 - \alpha T - 0.5(\alpha T)^2) \\ \alpha^{-2}(e^{\alpha T} - 1 - \alpha T) \\ \alpha^{-1}(e^{\alpha T} - 1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.9)$$

$$D_k^3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.167 T^3 \\ 0.5 T^2 \\ T \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.10)$$

where j is the length of D_k^i and $0_{m \times n}$ is a $m \times n$ matrix of zeros. The α is a positive constant corresponding to a "correlation time constant" for the acceleration and yields a model with a pole outside the unit circle. The ω is a turning rate and is computed from the 3DTR state estimates as the magnitude of the acceleration divided by the speed of the target. A constant acceleration model can be attained with the EIA or 3DTR by setting α or ω to a small number.

The kinematic constraint (KC) for constant speed targets can be utilized as additional information about the motion of constant speed, maneuvering targets [8,9]. The KC tends to force the acceleration estimates to change in a manner that is consistent with the dynamics of the target. The speed of a target is given by

$$S = (\dot{x}^2 + \dot{y}^2 + \dot{z}^2)^{1/2} \quad (4.11)$$

For a target moving at constant speed

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \dot{x}\ddot{x} + \dot{y}\ddot{y} + \dot{z}\ddot{z} = V \cdot A = 0 \quad (4.12)$$

where V and A are the target velocity and acceleration vectors, respectively. The KC is incorporated into the filter as a pseudomeasurement [9]. The pseudomeasurement equation is given by

$$\frac{V_{k|k}}{S_{k|k}} \cdot A_k + \mu_k = 0 \quad (4.13)$$

where

$$V_{k|k} = [\dot{x}_{k|k} \quad \dot{y}_{k|k} \quad \dot{z}_{k|k}], \quad S_{k|k} = (\dot{x}_{k|k}^2 + \dot{y}_{k|k}^2 + \dot{z}_{k|k}^2)^{1/2} \quad (4.14)$$

and $\mu_k \sim N(0, R_k^\mu)$. The μ_k is a white Gaussian error process that accounts for the uncertainty in both $V_{k|k}$ and the KC. Since the initial estimates of $V_{k|k}$ may be poor, R_k^μ is initialized with a very large value and allowed to decrease as

$$R_k^\mu = r_1(\delta)^k + r_0 \quad (4.15)$$

where $0 < \delta < 1$, r_1 is a constant chosen large for initialization, and r_0 is a constant chosen for steady-state conditions. The

Kalman filtering equations provide the time and measurement updates, with the time update performed with constrained values of the previous filter cycle. The filtering equations for utilizing the KC are given below with $X_{k|k}^c$ and $P_{k|k}^c$ denoting the state estimate and error covariance after the KC has been applied.

Constraint Update:

$$X_{k|k}^c = [I - K_k^c C_k] X_{k|k} \quad (4.16)$$

$$P_{k|k}^c = [I - K_k^c C_k] P_{k|k} \quad (4.17)$$

where

$$K_k^c = P_{k|k} C_k^T [C_k P_{k|k} C_k^T + R_k^\mu]^{-1} \quad (4.18)$$

$$C_k = \frac{1}{S_{k|k}} [0 \quad 0 \quad \dot{x}_{k|k} \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad \dot{y}_{k|k} \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad \dot{z}_{k|k}] \quad (4.19)$$

Simulation results demonstrating the benefits of the KC are given in [8,9]. When the KC is used in an IMM algorithm, it is applied to the state estimate and error covariance of a particular model after the mixing process and after the measurement update.

5. Calculating the Revisit Time

The IMM algorithm can be used to calculate the revisit time for the next measurement. The revisit time is determined on-line as the time when the predicted error covariance exceeds a given threshold of performance. When the target maneuvers, the uncertainty in the estimates and values of the error covariance increase and, as a result, the revisit period decreases. When the target stops maneuvering, the revisit time will increase.

The next measurement is scheduled when the predicted error covariance in position exceeds a given threshold. The revisit period, T , is computed such that

$$\bar{P}_{k+T|k} \leq \bar{P}_{th} \quad (5.1)$$

where $\bar{P}_{k+T|k}$ denotes the error covariance of the predicted position and \bar{P}_{th} denotes the threshold. Since $\bar{P}_{k+T|k}$ is a matrix and T is a scalar, the trace operator, Tr , is introduced and T is computed such that

$$Tr[\bar{P}_{k+T|k}] \leq Tr[\bar{P}_{th}] \quad (5.2)$$

Since $\bar{P}_{k+T|k}$ is monotone increasing with T , allowing T to be a maximum yields

$$Tr[\bar{P}_{k+T|k}] = Tr[\bar{P}_{th}] \quad (5.3)$$

The error covariance of the predicted position is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{P}_{k+T|k} = & \sum_{i=1}^3 \mu^i [F_p^i P^i (F_p^i)^T + G_p^i Q^i (G_p^i)^T] \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^3 \mu^i F_p^i X^i (F_p^i X^i)^T - \bar{X}_{k+T|k} \bar{X}_{k+T|k}^T \end{aligned} \quad (5.4)$$

where F_p^i is the state transition for position of model i , $G_p^i Q^i (G_p^i)^T$ is the associated process noise for position, and $\bar{X}_{k+T|k}$ is the predicted position at time T when all models are considered. Applying the trace operator to Eq. (5.4) yields

$$\begin{aligned} Tr[\bar{P}_{k+T|k}] = & \sum_{i=1}^3 \mu^i (Tr[F_p^i P^i (F_p^i)^T + G_p^i Q^i (G_p^i)^T]) \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^3 \mu^i Tr[F_p^i X^i (F_p^i X^i)^T] - Tr[\bar{X}_{k+T|k} \bar{X}_{k+T|k}^T] \end{aligned} \quad (5.5)$$

The $Tr[\bar{P}_{k+T|k}]$ of Eq. (5.5) is determined by expanding each term and collecting the coefficients of a polynomial in T . Since the prediction is a function of the next revisit time, F_p^i and G_p^i for the EIA and 3DTR must be modified by eliminating the exponential

and trigonometric functions. A second order Taylor expansion in T was used to include the functional dependence of α_p and ω_p , where p refers to values used for the prediction. The expansion of each term of Eq. (5.5) can be written as

$$\text{Tr}[\bar{X}_{k+T|k}\bar{X}_{k+T|k}^T] = \sum_{k=0}^8 f_k T^k \quad (5.6)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 \mu^i \text{Tr}[F_p^i X^i (F_p^i X^i)^T] = \sum_{k=0}^8 e_k T^k \quad (5.7)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 \mu^i (\text{Tr}[F_p^i P^i (F_p^i)^T] + G_p^i Q^i (G_p^i)^T) = \sum_{k=0}^8 g_k T^k \quad (5.8)$$

where f_k , e_k , and g_k determine the coefficients of T^k . Analytical expressions have been obtained for the coefficients and are given in [10]. By letting α_p or ω_p be zero, the coefficients for prediction with constant acceleration models can be obtained.

The threshold, \bar{P}_{th} , can be selected to maintain a given variance reduction relative to the measurements. Let

$$\text{Tr}[\bar{P}_{th}] = \lambda \text{Tr}[R_k] \quad (5.9)$$

where λ is a positive scalar that determines the variance reduction and R_k is the measurement error covariance. Usually radar measurements are in spherical coordinates while the tracking is performed in Cartesian coordinates. For spherical measurements, R_k can be approximated in Cartesian coordinates by

$$R_k = U \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_R^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & R^2 \sigma_B^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & R^2 \sigma_E^2 \end{bmatrix} U^T = U R_{RBE} U^T \quad (5.10)$$

where $U U^T = I$. Using the trace operator yields

$$\text{Tr}[\bar{P}_{th}] = \lambda \text{Tr}[U R_{RBE} U^T] = \lambda (\sigma_R^2 + R^2 (\sigma_B^2 + \sigma_E^2)) \quad (5.11)$$

The polynomial to calculate the revisit period, T , is

$$\text{Tr}[\bar{P}_{k+T|k}] - \text{Tr}[\bar{P}_{th}] = \sum_{k=0}^8 h_k T^k = 0 \quad (5.12)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} h_0 &= g_0 + e_0 - f_0 - \text{Tr}[\bar{P}_{th}] \\ h_j &= g_j + e_j - f_j, \quad j = 1 \dots 8 \end{aligned}$$

The revisit period is determined by solving Eq. (5.12) with Newton's method and maximum and minimum values for the sample period.

6. Adjusting of Energy Waveforms

The adjusting of energy waveforms can also be done using IMM algorithm. The accuracy of the state estimates is limited by the accuracy of the radar measurement system. Since the radar range error is relatively constant for a wide interval of signal to noise ratios, the limiting factor of measurement accuracy is due to the radar angular accuracy. By changing waveforms, different amounts of energy can be directed toward the target with higher energy waveforms having the potential to provide more accurate measurements. When the target maneuvers, the CV model probability becomes low and increasing the energy of the waveform when the probability of the CV model is below a threshold should provide better state estimates. After the maneuver, tracking with a lower energy waveform can be resumed. Since a higher energy waveform requires the radar to spend more time and energy on the target, an algorithm which efficiently allocates the radar time-energy budget is critical to effectively track maneuvering targets and search for new targets.

7. Radar Pointing

The pointing of the radar for the next measurement is crucial when tracking maneuvering targets. If the radar beam is improperly positioned, a measurement may not be available or a measurement from another target may be used to update the track. A simple pointing method is to use a constant velocity or constant acceleration model to predict the position of the next measurement using the current output state estimate. However, this method uses a single state estimate for the prediction and does not take into account the current dynamics of the target. The output of the IMM algorithm can be used to position the radar. Each state estimate is predicted with its own dynamics and then probabilistically weighted using the current model probabilities to form a predicted position. This predicted position can then be used to point the radar and set its range gate.

8. Simulation Results

The performance of CV and CVEIA3DTRKC IMM algorithm track filters is first compared for a maneuvering target. Second, a CVEIA3DTR prediction model is used to compute the revisit time from the output of a CVEIA3DTRKC track filter for a weapons control example. Third, the scheduling of radar waveforms is presented. A 1.0 km range gate and 2.0 degree beamwidth were used as a coarse gate when pointing the radar. Also, all measurements were gated using a 99 % confidence region and tracks were terminated if the measurement did not fall within the validation region and coarse gate for four consecutive updates. For the simulation study, no tracks were terminated or lost.

Comparison of CV and CVEIA3DTRKC Track Filters

A performance comparison of CVEIA3DTRKC and CV track filters is presented. The target is constant height and constant speed with an initial position and velocity of [36.7, 52.1, 0] km and [-175, -208, 0] m/sec, respectively, and performs a 3 g turn from 30 to 42 seconds and a 4 g turn from 52 to 62 seconds as shown in Fig. 8.1. A second order, critically-damped system with a natural frequency of 2 rad/sec was used to model the target response to acceleration commands. For the simulation study, a radar tracking system has zero-mean Gaussian measurements with standard deviations of 15 meters in range and 0.0025 radians in bearing and elevation.

The CVEIA3DTRKC track filter was designed as the one in [8] for the study. The process error covariance for the CV model filter was $Q_k = 625 I_3 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^4$, where I_3 is a 3×3 identity matrix. The CVEIA3DTRKC has process error covariances of $Q_k^1 = 1 I_3 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^4$, $Q_k^2 = 900 I_3 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^6$, and $Q_k^3 = 9 I_3 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^6$. The EIA correlation time constants are $\alpha = 0.11 \text{ Hz}$ for filtering and $\alpha_p = 0.05 \text{ Hz}$ for pointing and prediction. A KC variance of $(500(0.9)^k + 100(T^2 \text{Tr}[Q_k^2]/3)^{-1})$ was used for the 3DTR. Also, the 3DTRKC acceleration estimate was modified if its turning rate is not greater than 0.08 rad/sec for filtering and 0.05 rad/sec for pointing by scaling the accelerations estimates normal to the velocity vector. For the IMM algorithm track filters, the initial model probabilities were $\mu_0 = [0.9 \ 0.1 \ 0]$ with model switching probabilities

$$\Pi = \begin{bmatrix} 0.96 & 0.04 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.65 & 0.35 \\ 0.06 & 0 & 0.94 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8.1)$$

A technique for changing the model switching probabilities as a function of the sample interval was presented in [11]. The model switching probabilities are modified according to $\Pi(t) = \Pi^{t/t_{sw}}$, if the update interval t exceeds a minimum switching time interval t_{sw} . If the update interval is less than t_{sw} , the model switching probabilities are Π . The minimum switching time interval was $t_{sw} = 1.0 \text{ sec}$. For initialization, a 10 Hz update was used for the first second for all track filters. The Root-Mean-Square Errors (RMSE) of position and velocity for the two algorithms are given in Fig. 8.2 for a 2 Hz data rate and are an average of 200 Monte Carlo experiments. The IMM algorithm provides improved tracking performance when the target is maneuvering. The pro-

cess error covariance for the CV filter could have been chosen to match the performance of the IMM algorithm in the nonmaneuvering regions, but the estimation error in position would have been larger than the expected measurement error, as denoted by the line above the positional estimates. The filter standard deviations in position and velocity are given in Fig. 8.3. The filter standard deviations are the square root of the sum of the square of the position or velocity elements from the diagonal of the error covariance matrix. Note the change in the error covariance of the IMM algorithm track filter when the target maneuvers.

Adaptive Sampling for Maneuvering Targets

A comparison of track performance for the IMM algorithm with periodic and adaptive sample intervals is presented here. The 2 Hz periodic CVEIA3DTRKC track filter is compared with an adaptive CVEIA3DTRKC track filter using a CVEIA3DTR scheduling model. The KC variance for the adaptive filter was changed to $(200(0.9)^k + 100(T^2 \text{Tr}[Q_k^2]/3))^{-1}$ to attain a steady-state variance quicker. The results for the adaptive filter are an average of 2500 Monte Carlo experiments. Since the same sequence of measurement times was not used for each experiment, an average was made from the number of times each measurement time was chosen. The target trajectory is stored at a 10 Hz data rate and the measurement time nearest to the revisit time is chosen to update the track filter.

The state estimates for weapons control must be more accurate than those for surveillance and require the target track be updated more frequently. However, when the target is not maneuvering the number of revisits should be minimized to conserve the radar time-energy. To provide more measurements when the target is maneuvering, the scheduling parameter λ is changed as a function of the CV model probability. When the CV model probability is above 0.5, $\lambda = 1$, and when the CV model probability is below 0.5, $\lambda = .5$ to schedule more measurements. A comparison of adaptive sampling and periodic 2 Hz track filters is given in Fig. 8.4. When the target is maneuvering, the tracking performance for the two filters is very similar. However, the periodic filter has much better tracking performance than the adaptive sampling filter when the target is not maneuvering because the adaptive filter only updates the track in order to maintain a given level of performance. Thus, when the target is not maneuvering, the revisit times, as shown in Fig. 8.5, are large in comparison to the periodic track filter. Notice that the models respond well to the target modes for the adaptive track. The average number of updates is 198 for the periodic track and 92 for the adaptive track, which is a 54 % savings in overall updates. Approximately a 74 % saving in updates after initialization is realized in the nonmaneuvering region because the revisit periods are similar for both filters when the target is maneuvering. The number of updates for the periodic filter can be reduced, but the tracking performance in the maneuvering region would degrade in comparison to the filter with adaptive sampling. Another option is to change the update rate when the target is not maneuvering, but this option would have many of the problems associated with decision-directed techniques of single model track filters.

Scheduling of Radar Waveforms

Scheduling radar waveforms is presented in this section. The accuracy of the state estimates is limited by the accuracy of the radar measurement system. Since the radar range error is relatively constant, the degradation of the measurements is mainly due to the radar angular accuracy. A higher energy waveform is used when the CV model probability is below 0.5. To simulate the energy increase, an angular accuracy of 0.002 radians is used for the high energy waveform and 0.0025 radians is used for the lower energy waveform. A range error of 15 meters is used for both waveforms. The example has a periodic data rate of 1 Hz and compares the CVEIA3DTRKC track filter with and without scheduled waveforms. The tracking performance for position in the maneuvering region with the higher energy waveform is substantially better than with the lower energy waveform, as shown in Fig. 8.6. Since there is more uncertainty in the state estimates when a target is maneuvering, the accuracy of the state estimates

are improved by scheduling a higher energy waveform to decrease the measurement error.

9. Summary and Concluding Remarks

The scheduling of measurements to update target tracks using the output of the IMM algorithm has been presented. The output of the IMM algorithm can also be used to schedule resources, such as higher energy waveforms and possibly Doppler measurements, to provide better track performance for maneuvering targets. The IMM algorithm is the superior technique to tracking maneuvering targets and provides more information than a single model track filter. The use of the IMM algorithm eliminates the need for decision-directed approaches to tracking maneuvering targets and scheduling measurements. The IMM algorithm provides an on-line measure of tracking performance and measurements are scheduled when needed to maintain that performance. The savings can be used for other radar functions or to update additional target tracks. More familiarity with the scheduling algorithm is needed to realize its full potential. Other issues to investigate include the scheduling of measurements in a cluttered environment, track initiation, fluctuating targets, a probability of detection less than one, and the use of multiple sensors. The scheduling of measurements using the output of the IMM algorithm represents a significant contribution in the control of a phased array radar for the tracking of maneuvering targets.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Independent Exploratory Development (IED) Program and NSWCDD AEGIS Program Office, Naval Surface Warfare Center Dahlgren Division, Dahlgren Virginia.

References

1. S.S Blackman, T.J. Broida, and M.F. Cartier, "Applications of a Phased Array Antenna in a Multiple Maneuvering Target Environment," *Proc. of 20th IEEE Conf. on Dec. and Cont.*, San Diego, CA, Dec. 1981, pp. 1413-1418.
2. Y. Bar-Shalom, and T. E. Fortmann, *Tracking and Data Association*, Academic Press, Inc., Orlando, FL, 1988.
3. G. Van Keuk, and S.S Blackman, "On Phased-Array Radar Tracking and Parameter Control," *IEEE Trans. Aero. Elect. Syst.*, AES-29, 1993, pp. 186-194.
4. H.A.P. Blom, "An Efficient Filter for Abruptly Changing Systems," *Proc. of 23rd IEEE Conf. on Dec. and Cont.*, Las Vegas, NV, Dec. 1984.
5. H.A.P. Blom, and Y. Bar-Shalom, "The Interacting Multiple Model Algorithm for Systems with Markovian Switching Coefficients," *IEEE Trans. Auto. Cont.*, AC-23, Aug. 1988, pp. 780-783.
6. J.C. Tugnait, "Detection and Estimation for Abruptly Changing Systems," *Automatica*, 1982, pp. 607-615.
7. Y. Bar-Shalom, C.Y. Chang, and H.A.P. Blom, "Tracking a Maneuvering Target Using Input Estimation Versus The Interacting Multiple Model Algorithm," *IEEE Trans. Aero. Elect. Syst.*, AES-25, 1989, pp. 296-300.
8. G.A. Watson, and W.D. Blair, "IMM Algorithm for Tracking Targets that Maneuver Through Coordinated Turns," *Proc. of SPIE Signal and Data Processing of Small Targets 1992*, Orlando, FL, Apr. 1991, pp. 236-247.
9. W.D. Blair, G.A. Watson, and A.T. Alouani, *Use of Kinematic Constraint for Tracking Constant Speed Maneuvering Targets*, Naval Surface Warfare Center, NAVSWC TR 91-561, Dahlgren, VA.
10. W.D. Blair, G.A. Watson, *Multiple Model Estimation for the Tracking of Maneuvering Targets*, Naval Surface Warfare Center, NAVSWC TR 93-371, Dahlgren, VA.
11. W.D. Blair, and G.A. Watson, "IMM Algorithm and Aperiodic Data," *Proc. of SPIE Acquisition, Tracking, and Pointing VI* Orlando, FL, Apr. 1992, pp. 83-89.

Fig. 6.1. The Trajectory Profile

Fig. 6.3. CV and CVEIA3DTRKC Filter Standard Deviations

Fig. 6.5. Revisit Time and Model Probabilities

Fig. 6.2. CV and CVEIA3DTRKC Tracking Performance

Fig. 6.4. Adaptive and Periodic Tracking Performance

Fig. 6.6. Tracking Performance with Scheduled Waveforms